

MEASURING CONSTITUTIVE SHEAR BEHAVIOUR OF ORTHOTROPIC COMPOSITES AND EVALUATION OF THE MODIFIED IOSIPESCU TEST

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ABSTRACT: The modified Iosipescu test uses a variable notch opening angle θ , depending on the material anisotropy and orientation, to accomplish even stress- and strain fields in the test region. Constitutive shear properties can thus be measured more accurately, more completely, and with fewer sources of error. Here more materials and properties were studied, and a 3D optical strain- and displacement monitoring system was used to evaluate and improve both the modified test and the novel fixture used here. It performed substantially better than the Wyoming fixture in terms of producing constant through-specimen thickness conditions and preventing undesired specimen twisting. Additionally, loading-unloading behaviour of several high-performance unidirectional fiber composites was investigated to assess stiffness reduction, damage, localization, and irreversible strains. In the present of such, well controlled testing conditions are even more important.

KEYWORDS: Shear properties, modified Iosipescu test, anisotropy, strain field uniformity, comparison and evaluation of fixtures, optical 3D monitoring of strains and desired/undesired displacements

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

One key issue when testing for material properties is to achieve well controlled and well defined conditions in the test region. This is intricate in isotropic materials and even more so for composites, particularly when shear properties are addressed. Previously, the Iosipescu test[1] for in-plane shear properties of composite panels[2-,9] was modified to accommodate for a various degrees of material orthotropy[10,11]. By the introduction of the variable notch-opening angle θ , more homogeneous stress and strain fields were obtained in the test region. Using a rescaling operation[3,4], the resulting closed form expression (Eqn. 1) only depends on the ratio of moduli in the material principal directions which are generally more easily measured. The optimal notch opening angle is determined for each specific material tested. It relies on the best specimen geometry for isotropic materials[1, 10] as

$$\tan(\theta) = \frac{\tan(\theta_{\text{iso}})}{\sqrt[4]{\lambda}} \quad \text{where} \quad \lambda = \frac{E_y}{E_x} \quad (1)$$

where $2\theta_{\text{iso}} = 110^\circ$ and directions for E_x and E_y are shown in Figure 1 . The merits of this rescaling procedure were verified both numerically (using elastic FE-analysis) and experimentally[10]; very homogeneous strain fields were observed using a DSP-technique

(optical whole-field measurement), and also consistently confirmed with strain gages. Further, markedly higher shear strengths prior to first cracking were obtained compared to the standard test[2,9,10]. The former is paramount for accurate measurements of shear moduli (G_{12}) while the latter is important when determining the entire constitutive response in shear, i.e. $\tau(\gamma)$. Thereby, notable non-linear shear behaviour was observed already at low-to-moderate loads while marked ductile behaviour was obtained for higher shear strains. Experimentally, it is still difficult to determine G_{12} and $\tau(\gamma)$: strains must be measured on both front- and backside of the specimen. The main reason is that undesired specimen deformation, as e.g. twisting, can never be completely avoided with certainty [4,5,10].

The modified Iosipescu test has already been proven very successful[10], but tests on more materials (of different degrees of orthotropy, i.e. different λ) are needed to confirm these findings as being generally applicable. Further, several observations require additional studies to be fully understood. For once, an orthotropic material loaded in shear τ_{12} along its principal directions (1 and 2) should exhibit the same constitutive behaviour (prior to failure) regardless of how the fibers are oriented. Specifically, loading which nominally applies τ_{12} or τ_{21} should give similar results (and naturally G_{12} is the same property as G_{21}). Depending on how the specimen is cut from the material, Eqn. (1) specifies different notch angles, *viz.* wider or sharper than 110° , corresponding to evaluation for values λ or $1/\lambda$, respectively. Failure behaviour may, however, exhibit quite different modes and levels since damage propagation is mainly confined to one direction (*viz.* along the fibers)[7,8,10].

As shear stresses and strains increase, non-linear mechanisms will appear, possibly together with damage of various kinds. Such may come as microcracks, debonding, voiding, rearrangements on the molecular level etc. These phenomena (may) precipitate localization phenomena, and thus causing uneven strains and constitutive behaviour throughout the material volume in the test region. An obvious example are the multiple cracks between fibers when testing with those across the test region[8-10]. The θ -modified Iosipescu test[4,5] delays and diminishes errors due to localizations effects by means of producing more homogeneous global fields. However, when the global material behaviour is governed by more widespread damage and several localization sites, a robust test method should encompass that the onset of such may not occur in a perfectly symmetric fashion (within the rather small tested material volume). That is, damage onset (somewhere) should not instil undesired additional deformation, twisting or tilting, but continue to apply a well defined load. Particularly when testing repeated loading-unloading at increasing strains, occurring damage must not alter the general loading in the test region.

Another complication arises when testing high performing fiber composites with all (or a majority) of the fibers aligned; strongly anisotropic materials require wider notches (Eqn. 1) to test true material properties at higher stress levels which, in turn, require higher nominal loads and thus also higher clamping pressures in the clamped part of the specimen. Additionally, that clamping region is shortened (through the wide notched region) leading to even higher contact pressures at the highest loading points; i.e. the required point forces in an asymmetric four point bending (AFPB-) test to achieve a given shear force in the center increase with the distance between the two inner loading points. For this configuration, the fibers are aligned with the specimen length direction (and thus across the test region), the often observed clamping failure mode was crushing at the inner loading points[10]. Although not directly fatal for the test, such crushing would additionally enable non-symmetric load components as described above (and thus give poorer test results).

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD AND OUTLINE

The principal difference of the modified Iosipescu test is contained in Eqn. (1). The purpose is to create as homogeneous (elastic) fields as possible for any given tested material. The underlying analysis is approximate but quite robust and insensitive to the disregarded effects. A more detailed rationale, the theoretical analysis and background including sensitivity etc, can be found in Refs. [10,12]. The ASTM-standard prescribes notch angles of $2\theta = 90^\circ$ for composite panels[2], although isotropic materials in theory should use $2\theta > 102.6^\circ$, and commonly $2\theta_{\text{iso}} = 110^\circ$ is used in practice[10]. The practical implications for the modified test when testing an anisotropic composite can be seen in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 The Iosipescu specimen with a) ASTM standard notch ($2\theta = 90^\circ$), b) sharper notch opening with the fibers along, and c) wider notch opening with the fibers across the test region. Fiber directions (indicated) are assumed to be considerably stiffer.

In the present study, several different materials were studied experimentally, both composites of various anisotropy (λ -values) and directions, and aluminium (isotropic, i.e. $\lambda = 1$). Further, whole field strain- and displacement fields were recorded using an optical Aramis system (by GOM mbH, Germany) described in more detail in Refs. [9,10]. The monitoring was performed either two-sided 2D (specimen back and front) to establish uniformity and deformation symmetry, or one-sided 3D to monitor out-of-plane motion and displacements of both the specimens and the test fixtures.

The aluminium specimens ($2\theta_{\text{iso}} = 110^\circ$) are used for the evaluation and comparison of the Wyoming fixture with the in-house-built one[10], see Figure 2. Undesired (both in-plane and out-of-plane) deformation is the primary cause of error in the measurements. Whereas the two bending modes are undesired, specimen twisting is deemed to be the practically most detrimental type. Twisting inevitably results in different shear strains between specimen front and back side. Also, the in-house-built fixture is improved with respect to the specimen gripping, and thus the possibility of invoking undesired deformation from local effects in the clamped region. Figure 2 shows both the new fixture, the commonly used Wyoming fixture, and the additional clampers which apply pressure in the z -direction where it is deemed the most beneficial, *viz.* near the highest contact forces from the nominal- and clamping loads[6].

The composite materials are here tested both in monotonic loading and with repeated loading-unloading cycles with increasing maximum strain levels. From an accurate and entire $\tau(\gamma)$ -response, shear moduli, elastic limits etc are extracted. For the cyclic loading, several stiffness values are extracted, but it is not attempted to explain or quantify the micromechanical phenomena involved within the material. Some conceivable explanations for the same material loaded in through thickness shear are presented in Ref. [13], however.

Figure 2 a) Standard Wyoming fixture, b) In house built fixture, c) Details of the fixture function. New and aligned gripping, double guiding rods, window for strain measurements, suspension of the left fixture half and a clamping mechanism acting on the surface(z-direction) of the specimen.

EXPERIMENTAL: MATERIALS AND RESULTS

Material properties

Composite materials used are one panel of E-glass fibers epoxy 6x[0°] (central interface: CSM/roving) of thickness 5.3 mm (material #1) , see Table 1 , and one (uniaxial) panel consisting of 32 0°-layers oriented Fiberdux HTA/6376C carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg with a nominal panel thickness of 4.35 mm (material #2),see Figure 1 . The supplier reported elastic properties are given in table 1. Additionally, aluminum specimens (thickness 4 mm) were used for fixture evaluations (material #3), see Table 3 . Appropriate notch angles from Eqn. (1) are $2\theta_{\perp} = 125^{\circ}$ and $2\theta_{\parallel} = 95^{\circ}$ (material #1), $2\theta_{\perp} = 140^{\circ}$ and $2\theta_{\parallel} = 72^{\circ}$ (material #2) and $2\theta_{\text{iso}} = 110^{\circ}$ (material #3)

Table 1 Orthotropic elastic properties for a uniaxial glass fiber/epoxy composite

	Young's moduli [GPa]	Shear moduli [GPa]	Poisson's ratios [-]
By supplier	$E_1 = 40, E_2 = 12$	$G_{12} = 4.3$	$\nu_{12} = 0.25$
Measured	$E_1 = 56, E_2 = 20$	$G_{12} = 3.7$	$\nu_{12} = 0.30$ ($\nu_{21} = 0.13$)

Table 2 Orthotropic elastic properties for a uniaxial carbon fiber/epoxy composite, by supplier

Young's moduli [GPa]	Shear moduli [GPa]	Poisson's ratios [-]
$E_1 = 140, E_2 = 10$ ($E_3 = 10$)	$G_{12} = 5.2$ ($= G_{13}, G_{23} = 3.8$)	$\nu_{12} = 0.30$ ($= \nu_{13}, \nu_{23} = \nu_{32} = 0.50, \nu_{21} = \nu_{31} = 0.02$)

Table 3 Elastic properties for aluminum

Young's moduli [GPa]	Shear moduli [GPa]	Poisson's ratios [-]
$E = 70$	$G = 27$	$\nu = 0.30$

Material shear stress-strain responses and strain fields

The stress-strain response of the materials was measured on both sides of the specimen during testing. Both monotonic loading and cyclic loading was performed for both fiber orientations for each material, respectively. During monotonic loading (Figure 3 Figure 5) the agreement between the front and back-side of the specimen is very good. During cyclic loading (Figure 4

, Figure 6), the agreement is also very good but as the load increases and macroscopic damage evolves minor differences start to form. These differences may depend on both deviation from nominal conditions and difficulties to resolve the strain fields over evolving discontinuities and localizations. Further, as the specimen fails, surface features chip and introduce errors in the deformation measurements, and thus also affect the computation of the arising strains.

Figure 3 Stress-Strain relation for material 1 during monotonic loading. Fibers bridging the test region.

Figure 4 Stress-Strain relation for material 1 during cyclic loading. Fibers bridging the test region.

Figure 5 Stress-Strain relation for material 1 during monotonic loading. Fibers aligned with the test region.

Figure 6 Stress-Strain relation for material 1 during cyclic loading. Fibers aligned with the test region.

Figure 7 Stress-Strain relation for material 2 during monotonic loading. Fibers bridging the test region (only one sided strains recorded).

Figure 8 Stress-Strain relation for material 2 during cyclic loading. Fibers bridging the test region.

In Figures 9-11, representative strain fields are shown for both materials at intermediate and high load levels. Note the early formation of what seems to be localized damage in Figure 11 . In Figure 10 , a localization occurring at a later stage can be seen. These effects can also be seen Figures 15-16 where the evolving strain profiles are depicted for both orientations of material #1 (one sided). For same loads as in Figures 9-13, both back and front are seen in

Figures 13-14. Again, the front-to-back agreement of the global (average) strains is encouraging although they may differ locally (possibly due to uneven formation of damage).

Figure 9 Strain filed for material 2 with fibers bridging the test region. The nominal shear stress is 70MPa

Figure 10 Strain filed for material 2 with fibers aligned with the test region. The nominal shear stress is 60MPa

Figure 11 Strain filed for material 2 with fibers bridging the test region. The nominal shear stress is 40MPa

Figure 12 Strain filed for material 2 with fibers aligned with the test region. The nominal shear stress is 40MPa

Figure 13 Shear angle profile in the test region with fibers bridging the test region at 70 and 40MPa. Strains both on both sides of the specimen are presented.

Figure 14 Shear angle profile in the test region for fibers aligned with the test region at 60 and 40MPa. Strains both on both sides of the specimen are presented.

Figure 15 Shear angle profile with fibers bridging the test region and increasing load.

Figure 16 Shear angle profile for fibers aligned with the test region and increasing load.

From the cyclic load-unload responses seen in Figure 6 and Figure 8 unload secant moduli are extracted. These decay with increasing maximum attained shear strain as shown in Figure 17 and Figure 18. For both materials the decay is rather noticeable. For material #1, this decay differs to some extent depending on specimen orientation, however not exceedingly. For the carbon fiber/epoxy material (#2), the drop in secant modulus is more pronounced and occurs quite early in the test, see also Ref. [13] for related results.

Figure 17 Normalized secant modulus for material 1. Both specimen with fibers bridging and aligned with the test region were evaluated.

Figure 18 Normalized secant modulus for material 2. Fibers are aligned with the test region.

Monitoring fixture motion and deformation

The DSP-technique can also be used to monitor displacements, and this is done to compare the Wyoming fixture to the in-house-built one. Those tests were conducted on isotropic aluminium specimens, and at peak loads of roughly 9kN (corresponding to $\tau = 190\text{MPa}$). For the twisting deformation, the significant component is the z-displacement. Such fields are shown in Figure 19 and Figure 20. For, the in-house-built fixture, almost no displacement can be measured, whereas the one half of the Wyoming fixture distinctly rotates relative to the other. This trend is also manifested for the z-displacement of the specimen test region (Note that the scales differ one order of magnitude between the two set-ups).

Figure 19 Out of plane deformation in mm for a) the In house fixture and b) the aluminium specimen at a nominal load of 190MPa (9kN load on the fixture). The deformations were observed simultaneously.

Figure 20 Out of plane deformation in mm for a) the Wyoming fixture and b) the aluminium specimen at a nominal load of 190MPa (9kN load on the fixture). The deformations were observed simultaneously.

Figure 21 Recorded twisting motion of aluminium specimen at highest load.

Figure 22 Complete setup for measuring both fixture and specimen deformation in 3D.

In Figure 21 , the type of 3D results (z-displacement topography) obtained from DSP-measurements is shown illustrated. Note how the central specimen part is visibly twisted. In Figure 22 , the set-up using two 3D recording DSP-systems is shown. The inner cameras monitor the specimen while the outer record the fixture motions.

CONCLUSIONS

The θ -modified Iosipescu test is shown to produce reliable, repeatable and markedly more uniform shear (stress- and) strain fields for a range of materials. The most significant improvements are obtained for highest material anisotropy. Incidentally, the ASTM-standard specimen geometry ($2\theta = 90^\circ$) only works well for a quite anisotropic material (specifically for $\lambda = 4.15$) tested in the more compliant (most often the weaker) direction. Generally, avoiding strain concentrations of uncertain magnitude is paramount when testing materials. This is important even in the linear elastic regime, and even more so when establishing correct strengths, complete stress-strain responses, etc. The non-linearities arising and the gradual degradation, observed in both monotonic and cyclic loading was investigated for different materials. Materials with strongly anisotropic failure modes (due to e.g. strongly anisotropic internal structure, e.g. uniaxial fibers) also fail at different strains depending on the direction tested. However, up to that level, the results coincide. In the stronger direction (fibers across), the stress response can be studied after onset of multiple micro cracks, i.e. after localization of damage. Then, the specimen maintains its integrity even after widespread visible damage. How far these observations should be considered relevant depends on the practical loading situation and geometry. If the cracking/damage does not appear close to a free surface (as with the fibers aligned with the test direction), the markedly ductile material behaviour may be assessed also in practice.

The use of the DSP-technique was refined and resolved strain fields with better accuracy than in our previous work. Beginning damage and other localized effects were clearly discernable. The in-house-built fixture produced in essence identical strain levels (average in test region) on the specimen front and back faces. Even as the material visibly deteriorated, the test procedure maintained well controlled conditions (front-to-back differences of $\sim 0.4\%$ at global shear strains exceeding 8%). Thus, also the decay of stiffness (secant moduli etc) due to degradation in cyclic loading is reliable. The additionally applied pressure in the z -direction close to high contact forces successfully prevented damage in materials and configurations prone to crushing in the clamping region (incidentally the best performing ones).

Comparing the two fixtures by monitoring 3D displacements with the DSP technique showed notable relative twisting and even rotation (bending) motions for the Wyoming fixture (and the specimen). For the in-house-built fixture, these motions were smaller by one order of magnitude, also evidenced by the coinciding front-to-back strain readings.

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